

SECTION OF BIOLOGICAL AND MEDICAL SCIENCES

MYCOLOGICAL ASSESSMENT OF THE PHYTOSANITARY CONDITION OF FORAGE CROPS

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Abstract

The present study focuses on the analysis of the species diversity and phytopathogenic composition of the mycobiota associated with forage plants. The diverse chemical composition of forage plants, the specific features of fungus–substrate interactions, and the soil–climatic conditions of the investigated area have been found to influence both the species diversity and the phytopathogenic structure of the mycobiota. The results revealed that phytopathogenic fungi exhibited the highest species diversity on *Medicago sativa*, whereas the lowest colonization rate was observed on *Artemisia vulgaris*.

Keywords: forage crops, mycobiota, species diversity, phytopathogenic fungi, fungal diseases, phytosanitary status.

Azerbaijan is one of the countries with the most ancient agricultural traditions in the world. The effective use of traditional practices in the development of the agricultural sector of our country has yielded positive results, playing an important role in meeting the growing demand of the population for agricultural products [1;2]. However, in recent years, the negative effects of serious global bioecological imbalance have not bypassed our Republic. It should be noted that fungal pathogens inhabiting the environment recognize no boundaries; they migrate rapidly across neighboring countries and easily infect agricultural crops, including forage plants [3;4]. As a result, the productivity of forage crops decreases significantly, leading to substantial yield losses.

Therefore, before implementing measures to control fungal diseases of forage plants, it is of both scientific and practical importance to study the taxonomic identity of pathogens, their virulence level, and patterns of distribution [6;8].

The purpose of the present study was to investigate the species diversity and phytopathogenic composition of the mycobiota associated with forage crops recorded in the studied regions.

Materials and Methods

As the conditional research area, farms cultivating forage crops in the Bilasuvar, Jalilabad, and Imishli regions were selected. Samples were collected from both vegetative and generative organs of forage crops suspected to be infected by fungi. The “planned route and permanent plot selection” methods were used for sampling. In total, more than 400 samples were collected, and mycological analyses were conducted according to the objectives of the study.

Isolation and identification of phytopathogenic fungi into pure culture were carried out based on cultural–morphological and physiological characteristics using well-established methods [5;7;9].

All quantitative experiments were performed in at least 4 replicates, and the results were processed statistically according to standard approaches.

Results and Discussion

During the study, the following forage crops were examined: alfalfa (*Medicago sativa* L.), common vetch (*Vicia sativa* L.), field pea (*Pisum arvense* L.), maize (*Zea mays* L.), sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.), sugar beet (*Beta vulgaris* L.), and grass pea (*Lathyrus sativus* L.). As is well known, these forage crops are irreplaceable in livestock feeding systems.

It was found that the cultivation areas, resource potential, and chemical composition of forage plants directly affect the formation and species diversity of their mycobiota. Comparative analysis revealed that *Medicago sativa* had the richest mycobiota (23 species), whereas *Artemisia vulgaris* showed the lowest diversity (9 species) (Table 1). This difference is likely related to the chemical composition of the plants, fungus–substrate interactions, and the soil–climatic characteristics of the study regions.

Additionally, the phytopathogenic composition of the mycobiota formed on forage crops was analyzed. It was determined that *Medicago sativa* again had the highest number of phytopathogenic fungi (15 species), while *Artemisia vulgaris* had the lowest (4 species). As shown in Table 1, more than 65% of the mycobiota associated with alfalfa consisted of phytopathogenic fungi.

Among the dominant phytopathogens were *Botrytis cinerea*, *Erysiphe pisi*, *Fusarium moniliforme*, *F. oxysporum*, *Phoma medicaginis*, *Thielaviopsis basicola*, *Uromyces trifolii*, *U. repentis*, and *Verticillium dahliae*.

Species diversity and phytopathogenic composition of the mycobiota formed on forage

№	Fungal species	Artemisia vulgaris L.		Medicago sativa L.	
		Number of fungi	Number of phytopathogen	Number of fungi	Number of phytopathogen
1	<i>Alternaria alternata</i>	-	-	+	+
2	<i>A.tenuissima</i>	-	-	-	+
3	<i>Botrytis cinerea</i>	-	-	+	-
4	<i>Fusarium avenaceum</i>	-	-	+	-
5	<i>F.gibbosum</i>	+	-	+	+
6	<i>F.oxysporium</i>	+	+	+	-
7	<i>F.solani</i>	-	-	+	+
8	<i>F.semitectum</i>	-	-	-	+
9	<i>F.sporotrichoides</i>	+	-	+	-
10	<i>F.moniliforme</i>	-	-	+	-
11	<i>Erisiphe pisi</i>	+	+	+	+
12	<i>E.communis</i>	+	-	+	-
13	<i>E.cruciferarum</i>	-	-	-	+
14	<i>Phoma artemisia</i>	+	+	-	-
15	<i>Ph.betae</i>	+	-	+	+
16	<i>Ph.destructiva</i>	-	-	+	-
17	<i>Ascochita hordei</i>	-	-	+	-
18	<i>A.pisi</i>	+	-	+	+
19	<i>Cercospora fabae</i>	-	-	+	+
20	<i>C.beticola</i>	-	-	+	-
21	<i>Cladosporium herbarum</i>	-	-	+	+
22	<i>C.cladosporioides</i>	-	-	-	-
23	<i>Colletotrichium trifolii</i>	-	-	+	-
24	<i>Ramularia betae</i>	+	-	+	+
25	<i>R.medicaginis</i>	-	-	+	+
26	<i>Septoria pisi</i>	-	-	+	-
27	<i>S.tritici</i>	-	-	-	+
28	<i>Verticillium dahliae</i>	-	+	+	-
29	<i>Uromyces trifolii</i>	-	-	-	-
30	<i>U.fabae</i>	-	-	+	+

It is noteworthy that some phytopathogenic fungal species were found to colonize multiple forage crops simultaneously. This can be explained by the close taxonomic relationships and similar chemical compositions of these plants, as well as the comparable soil and climatic conditions of the study areas. These relationships are reflected in Table 1.

Overall, no epiphytotic outbreaks of any particular disease were observed in the studied regions, which indicates that the phytosanitary status of the area remains stable and not dangerous

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